

STYLISTIC ANALYSIS OF WORD COMBINATIONS AND SENTENCES DEPICTING THE 44-DAYS PATRIOTIC WAR**Akbarli T.***The teacher and PhD student of Baku Slavic University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236027>**Abstract**

The presented article is devoted to the stylistic analysis of sentences and word combinations formed in the context of the Second Karabakh War or the 44-days Patriotic War. No word or sentence is enough to describe the victory won by our brave sons and the valiant army of Azerbaijan which fought heroically in the Second Karabakh War. We proudly present to you only some of them. We believe that their analysis will form interesting ideas about the description and analysis of the war in the people reading the article.

Keywords: The Second Karabakh War, word combination, sentence, phonetic stylistic devices, lexical stylistic devices, syntactic stylistic devices.

Azerbaijan is a country with an ancient and glorious history, rich culture, literature and customs. In the history of every country, it is possible to witness not only honorable victories, but also tragedies and massacres that turned into bleeding wounds of the country. The Karabakh conflict has been a problem that has left tracks in the hearts of every Azerbaijani for many years. The elderly people and our parents who were witnesses of the First Karabakh war, remember the Karabakh fights and tragedy with sharp pain in their hearts. Notwithstanding the bloody history embracing these events, our nation never gave up and kept believing that the occupied lands would be regained thanks to the reasonable decisions of our President Ilham Aliyev and the strong army of Azerbaijan. On top of that, the reality about this conflict and the disgusting politics of Armenia and its supporters were explained to the growing young generation. The young born during the First Karabakh war and the following periods have always been brought up in the spirit of patriotism. The history of the occupation and the mass murder of population in Nagorno-Karabakh war have been depicted in various books, textbooks and articles. In our opinion, the heroic fight of the young generation, which constituted the main part of the Azerbaijani army in the 44-days war and further periods, is a clear evidence of patriotism. During the Second Karabakh war, countless young people joined the armed forces voluntarily, fought tooth and nail and died heroically.

Looking back on the history of Karabakh, we can clearly see that the dishonest policy of Armenians began many years ago. After the treaties of Gulistan (1813) and Turkmenchay (1828) concluded between Russia and Iran, the Russian state in a short time moved and settled 40,000 and 90,000 Armenians to the Karabakh region from Iran and Turkey respectively (1828-1830). Tsarist Russia started the "armenianization" process in Karabakh. Thus, the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan became a hotbed of conflict. At the beginning of the 20th century, the policy of ethnic cleansing became widespread in Karabakh. This resulted in the massacre of Turkish-Muslims by armed Armenians in 1905-1906 [1]. Armenians were able to strengthen themselves in Karabakh due to the comprehensive support of tsarism and the favorable conditions created by it. From the beginning of the 20th century, Armenians

systematically expelled Azerbaijanis from their historical lands, massacred and committed national genocide of them.

In 1991, Armenian armed forces started open military operations. On September 2, 1991, Armenian separatists announced the creation of an illegal "puppet" entity, the Republic of Nagorno-Karabakh, in Upper Karabakh. In 1992-1993, the territory of Nagorno-Karabakh and 7 other regions of Azerbaijan - Lachin, Kalbajar, Aghdam, Fuzuli, Jabrayil, Gubadli, Zangilan were occupied by the military forces of Armenia. As a result of military aggression by Armenia, 20 percent of Azerbaijani lands were occupied, more than 30,000 people were killed, up to 50,000 people were injured and maimed, up to 1 million Azerbaijanis became refugees and internally displaced persons, more than 4,581 people were captured and disappeared [4]. The first phase of the war ended with the officially signed armistice.

In response to the next attempt of military aggression by Armenia, the Azerbaijani Army launched a counter-offensive operation and as a result of the 44-days long Patriotic War, it succeeded in destroying the Armenian army, bringing it to its knees, and liberating the occupied territories. The "Iron Fist" operation carried out by the victorious Azerbaijani Army under the leadership of the Supreme Commander, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, was written in golden letters in the history of the Azerbaijani people and resulted in the surrender of Armenia [3].

The Karabakh conflict has been reflected on literature, art, social media, newspapers, radio and TV programmes, almost in all spheres of our life for many years. Another interesting fact is related with quotations, free and fixed word combinations which had been created on the process of the patriotic war. Such units expressing love for the homeland, heroism and bravery of Azerbaijani sons had been used in the languages and speeches of both authorities and citizens.

In the presented research project it is possible to get acquainted with interesting expressions and sentences, their translations into English, and semantic analysis. Such type of sentences depicting the heroism and dedication of martyrs, the atmosphere of the patriotic war and its consequences are the followings:

1. *Qanları ilə tarix yazan Şəhidlər* (Martyrs who wrote history with their blood) - the given epithet is a

lexical stylistic device in Azerbaijani. The literary device reflects that the occupied lands were regained at the cost of the blood and life of Azerbaijan's brave sons whom we owe our victory.

2. *Azərbaycan xəritəsini bütövləşdirən Şəhidlər* (Martyrs who unified the map of Azerbaijan) – the mentioned expression is an epithet in Azerbaijani. The expression symbolizes the bravery of the martyrs and their invaluable role in history. It is known that as a result of Armenia's military aggression, our ancient historical lands, which constitute 20 percent of Azerbaijan, remained under occupation for nearly 30 years. These lands were liberated from occupation through military and political means during the 44-days Patriotic War, and the territorial integrity of our country was restored. As it is seen from the given epithet, Azerbaijan achieved its territorial integrity years later precisely at the expense of the lives of martyrs.

3. *Qayıdan torpaqlardan qayıtmayan oğullar* (Sons who didn't return from the returned lands) - An interesting contrast is created by the means of antithesis. In the presented stylistic opposition, it is noted that although the lands of Azerbaijan were returned after 30 years, the sons of Azerbaijan, who fought in those lands to the last drop of their blood in the snow, frost, and the most difficult conditions, did not return from those lands.

4. *Qarabağın hər qarış torpağına Şəhid qanı səpələnib* (Martyr's blood was splattered on every inch of Karabakh's land) - Every inch of Karabakh's land is sacred, because these lands were watered with the blood of Azerbaijani sons who died both from enemy bullets during military operations and from landmines. In the given example, expressions such as “blood was splattered” and “lands were watered with blood” both have emotive meaning.

5. *Şəhidlər insanlığın ən uca fövqünə yüksəliblər. Ey insanlar, Qarabağ torpağına ayaq basanda asta basın, hər qarış torpaqdan Şəhid qanı fışqıracaq!* (Martyrs have risen to the highest level of humanity. O people, tread gently when you set foot on the land of Karabakh, the blood of martyrs will gush from every inch of the land!) - Martyrs gave their lives so that Azerbaijanis could live prosperously and happily in the lands liberated from occupation today, schoolchildren could study at school, and students could study at Karabakh University. We owe the freedom of these lands to them. We must not forget this reality in every inch of the land we step on. The expression “Martyrs' blood will gush from every inch of the land” has high emotional colouring.

6. *Əsrə bərabər bir ay* (A month equal to a century) – the given combination is an epithet in Azerbaijani. The expression symbolizes a glorious victory. Although the Second Karabakh War covered a short period, a great victory was achieved in this period. Thanks to this victory, Azerbaijan proved to the whole world that it is an independent country capable of ensuring the national interests of the people and the country. This victory showed the power of the Turkic world.

7. *Biz evimizə qayıdırıq* (We are returning home) - The given sentence expresses a broad meaning. Here, a lexical stylistic device, metonymy is used. Thus,

when we say “home”, we mean the ancestral lands of Azerbaijan, which have been under occupation for 30 years. These lands have belonged to Azerbaijan throughout history, and after many years we were able to return to our lands - our home. On the other hand, after returning to these lands people found their homes, renovated them, restored historical monuments, and even found the headstones of their ancestors and repaired broken ones.

8. *Heydər Əliyevdən İlham Əliyevə* (From Heydar Aliyev to Ilham Aliyev) - Throughout his meaningful life, the national leader Heydar Aliyev thought only about Azerbaijan, its modernization, strengthening, and prosperity. The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, is a worthy successor of the national leader Heydar Aliyev. The return of our ancestral lands was one of Heydar Aliyev's greatest dreams. He wanted to see Azerbaijan as a developed and independent country that is known all around the world. Ilham Aliyev was able to fulfill his father's dream, and this once again proved that he is both a wonderful son and a far-sighted and wise leader. We are proud of our president.

9. *Bir millət, iki dövlət/ Tək millət, iki dövlət* (One nation, two states) – In the presented expression we can come across the contextual antonyms. In fact, the words “one” and “two” are not antonyms separately. However, within the context, these two words are considered antonyms by creating a contrast. The mentioned expression reflects the great moral and military support shown by the neighbour country Turkey throughout history, as well as during the Second Karabakh War.

10. *Vətən savaşında tarixi zəfər* (A historic victory in the Patriotic War) – this is another vibrant epithet which depicts the importance of the victory gained in the patriotic war. This victory is engraved in the history of Azerbaijan with both its grandeur and its countless losses. Azerbaijanis will never forget this history.

11. *İşğaldan azad olunmuş ərazilərə “Böyük Qayıdış”* (“The Great Return” to the liberated territories) - The presented expression has a very broad meaning. The phrase “The Great Return” refers to the “return” of people who were forced to run away from their homeland barefoot and bareheaded 30 years ago. They returned back to their lands and homes that were unjustly taken from them. In this expression, the word “return” symbolizes the following ideas: Azerbaijanis will restore destroyed historical monuments, improve cities, and build schools, kindergartens, hospitals, and recreation areas that meet the most modern standards in these areas.

12. *İndi biz göstərdik kim-kimdir* (Now we have shown who is who) - The given expression in the Azerbaijani language uses both assonance, which is a phonetic stylistic device, and stylistic inversion, which is a syntactic stylistic device. Both the harmony of vowels and the violation of word order add special imagery to the given expression. Thanks to the victory gained in the second Karabakh war, Azerbaijan made its power known to the whole world. The whole world witnessed the restoration of Azerbaijan's territorial integrity. Now every country is aware of the power of

the Republic of Azerbaijan, which has rich history, literature, culture, customs and traditions.

The listed word combinations, expressions and sentences allow us to describe the process and results of the war in words. On the other hand, phonetic, lexical and syntactic stylistic devices such as assonance, epithet, metonymy, antithesis, stylistic inversion found in the presented examples express emotional colouring and form artistic quality and aesthetic values.

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